

Formation of foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan and its damaging factors

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Annotation: The article discusses the current developments in the establishment of foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan, as well as the training of special personnel in these languages.

Keywords: foreign language, personnel, education, foreign, Soviet, school, Russian, English, German, French, student, pupil.

Introduction. During the years of independence, the education system of our country was radically reformed. This process is clearly visible in all areas related to the field of education. The main goal of Uzbekistan in education was to train specialists who would meet the needs of international students in the socio-economic, political and cultural spheres. If until the 20th century, attention was paid to the study of Eastern languages and Russian, then from the 50s of the 20th century, the study of European languages was introduced. The resolutions of the Council of Ministers of the former USSR “On improving the teaching of foreign languages at school” and “On training teachers of foreign languages” in 1947 led to a certain revival of the teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan. The reason for the adoption of these resolutions was that until the second half of the 20th century, foreign languages were not taught in many schools in our country. In some schools where foreign languages were taught, only German was taught. In order to improve the teaching of foreign languages in the republic, work has been carried out in several directions.

- 1) Expanding and improving teacher training,
- 2) Establishing foreign language teaching in schools where foreign languages are not taught,
- 3) Targeted distribution of Western European languages being studied,
- 4) Providing educational institutions with educational literature,
- 5) Strengthening control over improving the quality of teaching,

Main part. The main problem facing the republic's public education system was the issue of establishing the teaching of foreign languages in all schools and the correct distribution of teaching of other Western European languages. The solution to this problem required providing schools and higher education institutions with foreign language specialists. Therefore, in January 1948, the second resolution of the former Soviet government “On the organization of training foreign language teachers” was adopted. The resolution indicated that the foreign language faculties of the Tashkent Pedagogical Institute and the Tashkent Evening Pedagogical Institute were not properly organized to train foreign language teachers from local youth.

To eliminate these shortcomings, the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages was established in 1948. In 1949, a correspondence department began operating at the institute, and in 1960, an evening department. In the first academic year, the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages was filled with applicants who could not enter other higher education institutions. Since these students did not have sufficient knowledge of foreign languages, a large number of them dropped out of the institute in the first year of study.

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The establishment of the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages could not fully solve the problem of foreign language teachers in rural areas. In this regard, in 1950, the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR adopted a resolution on organizing the training of foreign language teachers at the philological faculties of universities starting from the 1951-1952 academic year. In addition, 30 places were additionally allocated for Uzbek students from foreign language higher educational institutions of the Ukrainian SSR.

As we noted above, the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages admitted 117 students in the first direction in 1951, 154 in 1952, and 222 in 1953. In general, the number of personnel in foreign languages was to increase threefold over the five-year period. The number of students studying in the foreign language direction continued to grow in subsequent years. In the 1956-1957 academic year, 620 students studied English and 483 students studied German in the full-time departments of all higher educational institutions in the Republic. In the 1958-1959 academic year, 601 students studied English and 512 students studied German in the full-time department of the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages.

Unfortunately, in those years, representatives of the local ethnic group were not sufficiently involved in studying foreign languages. This was due to the difficulties faced by young people graduating from rural schools in entering higher education, as the lack of foreign language teachers in rural areas prevented them from completing their foreign language courses. Of the 370 students admitted to the Tashkent Institute of Foreign Languages in 1948, 12 (0.3%) were Uzbeks. A few years later, the number of representatives of the local ethnic group increased. In the 1956-1957 academic year, 545 out of 1,163 students (46%), in the 1961-1962 academic year, 997 out of 1,377 students (72%), and in the 1970-1971 academic year, 2,267 out of 2,672 students (84%) were Uzbek students. Thus, the problem of training foreign language teachers from among representatives of the local ethnic group was solved by the beginning of the 1970s.

Conclusion. In the second direction (establishing foreign language teaching in schools where foreign languages were not taught), in January 1941 the Council of People's Commissars of the Uzbek SSR adopted a resolution on improving the teaching of foreign languages in schools. According to it, the task was set to achieve the teaching of foreign languages in all schools starting from the 5th grade in the 1941/42 academic year, and in all rural schools by 1944. Pupils and students who received unsatisfactory grades in foreign languages were prohibited from being transferred to the next grade or course. However, the outbreak of war slowed down the implementation of this resolution. The expansion of foreign language teaching was also carried out by increasing the share of foreign language subjects in the curriculum of all schools, for example, in the 1946-1947 academic year, 395 hours were allocated for foreign languages, and starting from the 1947-1948 academic year, 462 hours were allocated. By 1959, according to the Ministry of Education of the Uzbek SSR, foreign languages were taught in 37% of schools in the republic. Starting from the 1961-1962 academic year, in classes with more than 25 students, it was established that foreign language lessons should be taught in two groups. Modern tasks were set for students, including the development of speaking, listening comprehension, reading and writing skills.

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Б Турсунов ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ SI-2

3 ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА УНИНГ ТАРИХИЙ БОСҚИЧЛАРИ: Турсунов Бехзодбек Андижон кишлоқ хўжалиги ва агротехнологиялар институти гуманитар фанлар ...

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6 EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN UZBEKISTAN

BB Tursunov УЧЕНЬИ XXI ВЕКА, 77